

Sowing Qualities of Seeds from Selected *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. Clones

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Abstract

Aim of this study is to analyse the sowing qualities from six selected *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. clones from the seed orchard on the territory of State Forest Enterprise Parvomay (Plovdiv district). Laboratory and soil germination, energy of germination and sowing norms were investigated. Results show difference in the investigated indices between the separate clones, which probably are genetically determined. Soil germination is with about 18% lower than the laboratory one. Clones suitable for production of black locust seedlings are Jazzkiseri, Appalachia and Pordim-4, whose genetic settings provide higher germination qualities of seeds compared to the rest of the clones.

Keywords: black locust, clone, half-sib progeny, germination

Introduction

Black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia* L.), which is multipurpose tree species, is assessed lately in many countries worldwide as one of the perspective species for production of biomass and energy plantations grown at higher density and short rotation (Gyuleva et al., 2013; Gyuleva, 2014; Geyer, 2006; Rédei et al., 2010, 2011).

The first black locust seed orchards in Bulgaria have been established in the 1980s, which has put the black locust management on a scientific basis (Donchev, 1989). Along with the development and improvement of a technology for vegetative propagation of the species with root cuttings (Naydenov et al., 1989; Broshtilov et al., 1998), the clonal frame for this species was introduced. Tsanov et al. (1992) publish the first results from testing the vegetative progenies of 34 selected black locust clones from 6 populations in North Bulgaria.

From the established plantations and orchards, forest reproductive material is obtained today, from which seedlings with valuable qualities are produced for the needs of forestry.

According to data from the laboratory of the Forest Seed-control Station in Sofia, decreasing of the vitality of black locust seed lots, originating from various regions of Bulgaria, is observed in the last 10 years. The literature review made for this study shows that there are no particular investigations of the sowing qualities of *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. seeds for the mentioned period. Similar investigations during the period from the 1950s until today are mainly directed to the ways of pre-sowing preparation of black locust seeds (Stefanov, 1951; Velkov, 1968; Mirzaei et al., 2013; Basbag et al., 2010; Abdullah et al., 2019; Christin et al., 2019).

The aim of this study is to analyse the sowing qualities of *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. seeds from six selected clones from the seed orchard on the territory of State Forest Enterprise Parvomay (Plovdiv district), which have shown good results according to growing indices at testing of their vegetative progenies in previous investigations (Tsanov et al., 1992).

Materials and Methods

Objects of investigation are seeds from six selected *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. clones, collected from vegetative seed orchard of State Forest Enterprise Parvomay next to Mechka reka nursery. The orchard was established in 2004 at a scheme 8x8 m and includes 37 clones. For the control, a total collection of seeds is used with provenance from vegetative seed orchard located in the forest nursery Lukovit (State Forest Enterprise Lesidren).

Laboratory sowing qualities of the obtained seeds were tested in the Forest Seed-control Station – Sofia according to the ISTA method.

For determining of the soil germination of clones, an experiment in the forest nursery Lokorsko was carried out in seed rows– in 3 repetitions at a scheme shown on figure 1. The seed rows includes 7 rows with a length of 1 m and a distance of 10 cm between the rows in which seeds are sown according to the scheme of each clone. Sowing was made on 15 May according to the norms established by the Forest Seed-control Station – Sofia. Results were checked every 5th day, and the last one was on 5 June.

Pre-sowing preparation of the black locust seeds was made after the method of three times dipping in hot water followed by cooling. This method has been recommended as efficient and safe (Stefanov, 1951; Velkov, 1968; Mirzaei et al., 2013; Basbag et al., 2010; Abdullah et al., 2019; Christin et al., 2019). With the aim of better scarification, ice has been added to the cooling water.

Legend: 1 – clone Pordim 4; 2 – clone Jaszkeseri; 3 – clone Oryahovo 5; 4 – clone Appalachia;
5 – clone Pordim 1; 6 – clone Ryahovo 7; K – control

Fig. 1. Sowing scheme of black locust seeds in seed rows

Sowing was made in an universal substrate with the characteristics: medium fraction (0 - 40 mm), composition (in 250 l scale: 70 % bright peat 0 - 40 mm, 30 % black peat 0 - 40 mm, 1 kg NPK 14-16-18, 50 g trace elements and Tenzid – moisturising agent, pH 5,5 - 6,5).

The sowing rate is determined according to the formula from Annex №7 of the Ordinance №4 from 15.02.2012 on the terms and conditions for registration of forest nurseries, as well as for the production of seedlings in forest nurseries – state property.

$$D = 10 \cdot O \cdot M / C \cdot G_s \cdot K, \text{ where}$$

D – density of the sowing

O – optimal number of ponies per 1 m (number of annual seedlings according to Annex №7 of the Ordinance №4 + 20%reserve for waste)

G_s – germination of seeds from the batch

M – mass of 1000 seeds from the batch

C – purity of the seeds in %

K – correction factor for soil germination of seeds (<1, established experimentally)

Results and Discussion

The management of genetic resources of forest tree species and their efficient conservation depend on sowing qualities of seeds, which differ at various provenances of many species from family Fabaceae, including black locust (Rajora, Mosseler, 2001; Tozer, Ooi, 2014; Safdar et al., 2021; Andrea et al., 2022).

After carrying out of analyses of sowing qualities of clone lots and the control it was established that the average mass of 1000 seeds varies from 17.5 to 22.7g. The laboratory germination is with average value 31.9% and varies from 7% to 59%. With highest germination are seeds from clones Jazzkiseri and Appalachia, and the first one is with 12% more, and the second one – with 27% lower than the control (52%). The energy of germination on the seventh day (E_{K7}) varies from 6 to 54%, and its average value is 28.7% (table 1).

On the basis of physical characteristics and laboratory germination, sowing norms of the lots of different clones were determined; they are shown on table 1. The index values vary in wide range – from 0,96 to 8,25 g/m. The average value of the sowing norm is 2,7 g/m. Correlation between germination and seeds mass was not determined.

Obtained results show that with highest soil germination are clones Jazzkiseri and Appalachia, the first one being with 14% higher and the second one – with 31% lower than the control (45%). The average soil germination is 26,3%. Germination of seeds begins between the 5th and the 10th day from the start of sowing and ends up to the 20th day. Percent of the germinated seeds on the 20th day varies from 5 to 52%, and its average value is 26,3 % (table 2). The dynamics of seeds germination, however, is different for the various clones and this aspect should be taken into account at the providing of reproductive material in connection with the final aim (Giuliani et al., 2019).

Table 1. Qualities of sowing materials according to clones and control in laboratory conditions

Clone from <i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> L.	Location (forest enterprise)	Kind of source	Kind of seed analysis	Index				
				Purity	Abs. mass	Laboratory germination	Ек7	Sowing norm
				%	G	%	%	g/m
<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>
Pordim – 4	Plovdiv/ Parvomay	Vegetative seed orchard	Germination after scarification	99	19,9	31	24	1,63
Jazkiseri	Plovdiv/ Parvomay	Vegetative seed orchard	Germination after scarification	99	19,8	59	54	0,85
Oryahovo – 5	Plovdiv/ Parvomay	Vegetative seed orchard	Germination after scarification	99	17,5	21	20	2,12
Pordim – 1	Plovdiv/ Parvomay	Vegetative seed orchard	Germination after scarification	99	22,7	7	6	8,25
Ryahovo – 7	Plovdiv/ Parvomay	Vegetative seed orchard	Germination after scarification	99	20,7	15	13	3,51
Appalachia	Plovdiv/ Parvomay	Vegetative seed orchard	Germination after scarification	99	20,7	38	35	1,39
Control	Lukovit	Vegetative seed orchard	Germination after scarification	99	19,6	52	49	0,96
Average values:				99	20,1	32	28,7	2,7

It is seen from the analysis that the laboratory and soil germination of seeds is highest for the clones Jazkiseri, Appalachia, Pordim-4 and the control. The applied multi-rank Duncan criterion identifies well-expressed and statistically significant differences in the average values of the laboratory germination of seeds in various clones ($F=855.400$, $df=6$, $Sign. = 0.001$), and the same one is observed in the soil germination, as well ($F=890.714$, $df=6$, $Sign.= 0.001$).

Table 2. Qualities of sowing materials according to clones and control in seed rows

Clone from <i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> L.	Location (forest enterprise)	Kind of source	Kind of pre- sowing preparation	Index						
				Purity	Abs. mass	Soil germination	Date of report			
							15 May	20 May	25 May	31 May
							Percent of germination according to days; date of establishment 15 May			
%	G	%	E5 %	E10 %	E15 %	E20 %				
<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>
Pordim – 4	Plovdiv/ Parvomay	Vegetative seed orchard	scarification	99	19,9	24	0	19	21	24
Jazkiseri	Plovdiv/ Parvomay	Vegetative seed orchard	scarification	99	19,8	52	8	38	47	52
Oryahovo – 5	Plovdiv/ Parvomay	Vegetative seed orchard	scarification	99	17,5	16	0	9	14	16
Pordim – 1	Plovdiv/ Parvomay	Vegetative seed orchard	scarification	99	22,7	5	0	3	5	5
Ryahovo – 7	Plovdiv/ Parvomay	Vegetative seed orchard	scarification	99	20,7	11	0	9	11	11
Appalachia	Plovdiv/ Parvomay	Vegetative seed orchard	scarification	99	20,7	31	3	18	29	31
Control	Lesidren/ Lukovit	Vegetative seed orchard	scarification	99	19,6	45	6	36	43	45
Average:				99,0	20,1	26,3	5.7	18.9	24.3	26.3

This presumes the existence of a correlation between the seeds provenance for both types of germination, which probably are genetically determined.

In case that these clones are used for seedling production, of an interest would be also the testing of qualities of their half-sibs progenies with a view to obtain qualitative sowing material.

Conclusion

The analyses of sowing qualities of seeds from selected *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. clones in the present study showed that there is a correlation between the seeds provenance and their laboratory and soil germination.

Soil germination is about 18% lower than laboratory germination, which shows that the applied pre-sowing preparation and the selected substrate for sowing are the right ones and have provided optimal conditions for seeds development.

Clones Jazskiseri, Appalachia and Pordim-4 are suitable for the production of black locust seedlings, whose genetic endowments provide higher germination qualities compared to the rest of the clones. *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. is propagated both by seed and vegetatively. The methods of vegetative propagation may to be applied to these clones. Depending of the purpose for which the plantations are created, seed production of seedlings is much easier and cheaper method.

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